

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PROGNOSTIC FEATURES OF HEMATOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS IN PATIENTS COVID-19 INFECTED

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to evaluate the features of hematological and biochemical parameters in persons infected with the SARS-CoV-2 virus and clinical manifestations of a systemic inflammatory response in patients complicated by pneumonia.

The object of the study was archival materials and electronic medical data of the Yeni Clinic in Baku City, which are mainly reserved for patients with COVID-19. Patients with positive and suspicious RT-PCR results were subjected to the study. In the course of the work, a complete blood count, biochemical blood parameters, interleukin-6 (IL-6), C-reactive protein (CRP), procalcitonin (PCT), levels of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), ferritin and D-dimer were analyzed. This study was retrospective, using electronic medical records and case histories of 251 patients with positive CT scans for pneumonia. Laboratory results of all patients were monitored both at admission and at discharge.

The results of the studies showed that these indicators are largely related to the severity of the disease.

Keywords: COVID-19, lymphocytes, CRP, D-dimer, ferritin.

Introduction

The coronavirus disease (2019) pandemic resulting in acute respiratory syndrome has affected the lives of millions of people around the world. Investigate the biological processes underlying the pathophysiology of COVID-19 has necessitated scientific research

A member of the human coronaviruses, SARS-CoV-2 is a positively polarized single-stranded RNA virus. The novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 belongs to the subfamily of β -coronaviruses and contains 79.5% of the genetic sequence of SARS-CoV, the causative agent of the epidemic that began in 2002 and ended in 2004.

Compared with SARS-CoV-2, like other SARS-CoVs and MERS-CoVs, patients with COVID-19 infection have a significantly higher fever, less respiratory distress, gastrointestinal symptoms, high blood cytokine profiles, multiple organ damage, and lower mortality. being significantly different from clinical symptoms. In addition to an unusually high transmission level, these also indicate a different pathological mechanism underlying human infection [1][2].

Examination of hematological parameters revealed that lymphopenia was clearly associated with disease severity. The number of other blood cells, including leukocytes, neutrophils, eosinophils, and platelets, may play a partial predictive role in determining the severity or severity of disease progression [3]. They investigated the relevance of key laboratory biomarkers

directly related to clinical features, such as elevated neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) in patients with a more severe course [4].

Some studies have studied neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) and CRP to identify potential clinical predictors by analyzing differences between severe and mild COVID-19 patients. Mousavi S. and others [5] during COVID-19, 14 (20%) patients with severe course and 56 (80%) patients with mild course (average age - $42.7 + 12.4$, 40 (57.1%) of them were men, the rest were women) were examined for their data. Leukocytes and NLR were significantly higher in severe patients than in non-severe patients ($p < 0.001$). Correlation analysis was performed to determine the relationship of NLR with leukocyte and CRP levels in severe and non-severe patients. In critically ill patients, the results showed that NLR was positively correlated with CRP levels ($R = 0.23$) and negatively correlated with leukocytes ($R = -0.38$).

Changes in lymphocyte counts, CRP, and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ERS) rates have been previously reported in Covid-19 patients, but little has been reported on their correlation with disease severity. Serum CRP levels were found to be higher in severe patients than in moderately severe patients. Elevated serum PCT and CRP levels are observed in patients with cardiovascular disease COVID-19 infected [6]. When examining the effect of secondary bacterial infection on the course of the disease, it was observed that bacterial

co-infection aggravated the process during the course of COVID-19. At this time, a high amount of PCT was observed [7].

Liu F. et al. [8] investigated the ability of IL-6, CRP, and PCT to predict mild and severe cases of COVID-19. Observations have shown that the severity of COVID-19 can be predicted by the determination of IL-6, CRP and PCT. IL-6 is the main trigger for the cytokine storm. CRP is a protein induced by IL-6 in the liver, which increases rapidly during liver inflammation. A high PCT level indicates that covid-19 patients may have a bacterial infection. All three biomarkers provide the right approach to treatment during severe COVID-19. Some researchers have noted that an increase for PCT during the acute course of COVID-19 is observed in the prognosis of the disease. It has been reported that fatal outcomes during the process are accompanied by a cytokine storm, and the severity of the disease depends on the cytokine storm syndrome [9] [10].

Some studies have been devoted to the role of ferritin during COVID-19. Linlin C., Li H., in their research to determine the role of ferritin infected people, found an increase in ferritin levels due to cytokine storm and secondary lymphohistocytosis in severe COVID-19 patients [11]. A similar study found that serum ferritin levels, as well as CRP and lymphocyte counts, were independent risk factors for the severity of COVID-19 disease and that patients who died had higher serum ferritin levels [12]. The association of iron homeostasis with the severity of COVID-19 disease has also been investigated [13]. It has been shown that the average indicator of ferritin concentration is 3-4 times higher in patients who die from COVID-19 than in patients who survive. Changes in ferritin levels are directly proportional to the nature of the disease, as ferritin levels rise in patients with increasingly severe diseases. Ferritin monitoring during hospitalization may help identify critically ill patients and predict the progression of COVID-19 to a worse clinical prognosis.

Chang L. et al. [14] conducted a multicenter retrospective study to investigate the possibility that elevated serum LDH levels in COVID-19 patients could help assess disease severity. Based on the ROC analysis, it was determined that the serum LDH level could predict the severity of COVID-19. A meta-analysis by Chen X. and colleagues [15] showed that the level of LDH may be useful in predicting the progression of COVID-19 to a more severe condition.

The D-dimer level is the most important indicator of the severity of the COVID-19 disease. A positive correlation of D-dimer values with age, length of hospital stay, lung damage, fibrinogen, and neutrophil count, but a negative correlation with lymphocyte count was observed. Some researchers have investigated the differences in D-dimer levels during the course of COVID-19 disease along with other major diseases. The early stage of disease is accompanied by activation of blood coagulation with high D-dimer, long prothrombin time (PT), and high fibrinogen level. Conditions such as diabetes, cancer, stroke, and pregnancy can cause an increase in D-dimer levels in COVID-19

patients. Measuring the level of D-dimer and coagulation parameters at the initial stage of the disease can facilitate treatment control [16]. It is known that biomarkers always play an important role in clinical decision-making in various infectious diseases. For this purpose biomarkers such as lymphocytes, platelets, D-dimer, LDH, CRP, ferritin, PCT were investigated in information systems. In the studied literature data, patients are divided into 3 groups according to the severity of the disease: mild, severe and critical group. In mild cases, clinical symptoms are weak, and pneumonia is not observed. In severe cases, fever, respiratory tract infection, shortness of breath and pneumonia may appear. In the critical group, pneumonia, severe acute respiratory infection, kidney, heart, lung and liver failure and even death may occur.

The state policy in the field of immunoprophylaxis in Azerbaijan is aimed at limiting and eliminating the spread of infectious diseases and preventing morbidity and mortality among the population. For this purpose, conducting research in various directions is being conducted in the direction of timely diagnosis of the disease and taking necessary measures, as well as evaluating the effectiveness of vaccination against a new type of coronavirus infection.

Research goals and objectives

The aim of the study was to evaluate hematological, biochemical parameters and clinical manifestations of a systemic inflammatory response in patients infected with the SARS-CoV-2 virus.

Materials and methods of research

The studies were carried out at the Yeni Clinic, which specializes in patients with COVID-19. To do this, a retrospective analysis of data from patients with positive and suspicious RT-PCR results was carried out based on case histories and an electronic database.

A total of 251 patients diagnosed with Covid-19 were included in this study. Cobas 6000, Sysmex XN 1000 Hematology inurement, Roche real-time PCR were used for testing. The control of the initial laboratory parameters of all patients was carried out both at admission and at discharge.

A complete blood count, biochemical blood parameters, such indicators as Interleukin-6, C-reactive protein, procolcytonin, lactate dehydrogenase and D-dimer were studied and evaluated.

Results

A total of 251 patients, 119 men, and 132 women, were included in this study. The mean age was 59.4 ± 1.3 . The most common age group was 45-75 years. Patients had mild, moderate, and very severe symptoms at the time of admission to the clinic, and therefore 123 (49%) were hospitalized, and the rest 128 (50.99%) were placed in intensive and intensive care units. 70 (27.8%) patients were in the intensive care group, and 58 (23.1%) patients were in the intensive care group. 159 (63.3%) patients had at least one major comorbidity, the most common of which were chronic diseases such as hypertension (36%) and diabetes (23%). Examining the patients' symptoms at the time of admission, it was determined that the median interval from the onset of symptoms to hospitalization for all patients was 7 days. The most common symptoms were fatigue

(81%), cough (63%), fever (57%), chest tightness or shortness of breath (32.7%). 35.7% of them complained of gastrointestinal symptoms, including nausea, diarrhea, loss of appetite, abdominal pain, and vomiting.

Differences in age, hemoglobin, leukocyte, NLR, neutrophil, lymphocyte, eosinophil, D dimer, CRP, procalcitonin, LDH, creatinine, urea, AST, glucose, GGT and ferritin levels at admission between the two groups were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) (Table 1).

On the day the patients were admitted to the hospital, the result of the general blood analysis showed a normal leukocyte count of 73.4% in most of the patients. Thus, this number was 10.4 ± 0.8 in intensive care patients, and 6.9 ± 0.3 in inpatients. The amount of hemoglobin was 12.7 ± 0.2 in the resuscitation group, and 16.5 ± 1.7 in the inpatient group. Lymphopenia was

common in 81.4% of patients. It is interesting that eosinopenia was found in more than half of these patients, 69.3%. In other laboratory results, an increase in the concentration of CRP (86%), PCT (73%), D- dimer (67%), ferritin (65%), LDH (70%), and creatinine (57%) was observed.

Thus, during COVID-19, some hematological and biochemical markers make it possible to determine the severity of the disease in time and predict the course of the disease. Among the two groups of severe ($n=70$) and very severe ($n=58$) that we investigated, among the specific biomarkers during COVID-19, a decrease in the number of lymphocytes and a significant increase in NLR, CRP, PCT, D-dimer, LDH and ferritin were observed (Table 2).

Table 1

Laboratory characteristics of patients infected with SARS-CoV-2
(Resuscitation and inpatient) (M $\pm$ m)

Parameters	Reanimation (n=128)		Stationary (n=123)	
	before	after	before	after
Age	60,2 $\pm$ 1,2		57,3 $\pm$ 1,4	
Bed days	17,5 $\pm$ 0,9		10,5 $\pm$ 0,5*	
Gender	K.-56 (43,7%) Q.-72 (56,3%)		K.-63 (51,2%) Q.-60 (48,8%)	
WBC(4,5-11,0)	10,4 $\pm$ 0,8	13,01 $\pm$ 0,6	6,9 $\pm$ 0,3*	7,8 $\pm$ 0,3**
HGB(125-174)	12,7 $\pm$ 0,2	11,4 $\pm$ 0,2	16,5 $\pm$ 1,7*	12,8 $\pm$ 0,2**
HCT(37-51)	38,3 $\pm$ 0,5	35,9 $\pm$ 0,6	39,6 $\pm$ 0,5	39,3 $\pm$ 0,5**
PLT(130-400)	248,7 $\pm$ 11,4	255,1 $\pm$ 12,5	242,1 $\pm$ 8,4	316,3 $\pm$ 11,8**
LYM(1,6-3,8)	1,51 $\pm$ 0,3	2,2 $\pm$ 0,5	1,3 $\pm$ 0,05	1,8 $\pm$ 0,08
NEUT(1,8-6,98)	9,8 $\pm$ 1,1	12,6 $\pm$ 1,2	5,3 $\pm$ 0,3*	9,9 $\pm$ 4,6
EOS(0,03-0,59)	0,02 $\pm$ 0,008	0,13 $\pm$ 0,01	0,03 $\pm$ 0,01	0,1 $\pm$ 0,01
CRP(0-5)	137,6 $\pm$ 9,1	96,1 $\pm$ 10,3	87,9 $\pm$ 7,6*	26,8 $\pm$ 3,9**
PCT(0-0,05)	1,58 $\pm$ 0,7	3,8 $\pm$ 1,1	0,1 $\pm$ 0,01*	0,1 $\pm$ 0,01**
BUN(19-47)	52,1 $\pm$ 3,7	64,6 $\pm$ 5,6	33,9 $\pm$ 3,1*	28,0 $\pm$ 1,3**
KREA(0,7-1,2)	1,22 $\pm$ 0,1	1,8 $\pm$ 0,2	0,9 $\pm$ 0,02*	0,8 $\pm$ 0,02**
ALT(12-40)	41,9 $\pm$ 2,7	47,7 $\pm$ 3,6	47,7 $\pm$ 3,9	51,7 $\pm$ 3,4
AST(19-48)	59,1 $\pm$ 3,3	69,1 $\pm$ 9,9	43,5 $\pm$ 2,6*	39,0 $\pm$ 2,8**
ALB(3,5-5,2)	3,4 $\pm$ 0,04	3,2 $\pm$ 0,04	3,9 $\pm$ 0,04	3,6 $\pm$ 0,04
GGT(7-46)	128,7 $\pm$ 14,4	127,8 $\pm$ 13,9	63,0 $\pm$ 6,4*	57,7 $\pm$ 5,5**
GLUK(82-115)	178,5 $\pm$ 9,3	166,8 $\pm$ 7,1	139,9 $\pm$ 5,6*	135,7 $\pm$ 5,7**
LDH(135-225)	539,0 $\pm$ 20,7	615,8 $\pm$ 57,2	347,3 $\pm$ 16,3*	262,7 $\pm$ 10,9**
FERR.(15-150)	1459,9 $\pm$ 219,2	1662,8 $\pm$ 442,6	646,4 $\pm$ 61,8*	490,9 $\pm$ 43,5**
INR (0,8-1,24)	1,21 $\pm$ 0,02	1,45 $\pm$ 0,05	1,2 $\pm$ 0,1	1,4 $\pm$ 0,1
PT(9-14,8)	14,3 $\pm$ 0,8	15,8 $\pm$ 0,7	13,1 $\pm$ 1,0	13,1 $\pm$ 0,2
D-DÍMER(0-500)	3718,0 $\pm$ 503,4	3968,0 $\pm$ 592,7	522,3 $\pm$ 36,8*	475,7 $\pm$ 40,3
SPO2(95-98)	82,2 $\pm$ 1,1	89,1 $\pm$ 1,6	94,3 $\pm$ 0,04*	95,9 $\pm$ 0,5

$p < 0,05$ ** statistical reliability between groups

Table 2

Depending on the severity of SARS-CoV-2 infection in patients as laboratory characteristic (M±m)

Parameters	All patients. (n=128)		Seriously i. p. (n=70)		Very Seriously i. p. (n=58)	
	before	after	before	after	before	after
WBC	10,4 ± 0,8	13,01 ± 0,6	9,7 ± 0,6	9,5 ± 0,6	10,1 ± 0,9	17,3 ± 0,9
HGB	12,7 ± 0,2	11,4 ± 0,2	12,6 ± 0,2	11,4 ± 0,2	12,8 ± 0,3	11,3 ± 0,3
HCT	38,3 ± 0,5	35,9 ± 0,6	38,5 ± 0,7	35,4 ± 0,7	38,2 ± 0,8	36,7 ± 0,9
PLT	248,7 ± 11,4	255,1 ± 12,5	273,4 ± 17,8	285,5 ± 16,7	218,9 ± 11,8	218,4 ± 17,9
LYM	1,51 ± 0,3	2,2 ± 0,5	1,06 ± 0,06	1,75 ± 0,1	2,1 ± 0,6	2,7 ± 1,1
NEUT	9,8 ± 1,1	12,6 ± 1,2	7,9 ± 0,6	7,5 ± 0,6	12,1 ± 2,4	18,9 ± 2,4
EOS	0,04 ± 0,008	0,13 ± 0,01	0,05 ± 0,01	0,16 ± 0,02	0,03 ± 0,01	0,09 ± 0,01
CRP	137,6 ± 9,1	96,1 ± 10,3	126,2 ± 11,4	48,1 ± 10,6	151,2 ± 14,4	154,1 ± 15,9
PCT	1,58 ± 0,7	3,84 ± 1,1	0,54 ± 0,1	0,69 ± 0,23	2,8 ± 1,5	7,6 ± 2,4
BUN	52,1 ± 3,7	64,6 ± 5,6	40,3 ± 3,5	38,7 ± 3,2	66,1 ± 6,5	96,0 ± 10,4
KREAT	1,22 ± 0,1	1,8 ± 0,2	1,1 ± 0,1	1,04 ± 0,1	1,38 ± 0,2	2,75 ± 0,3
ALT	41,9 ± 2,7	47,7 ± 3,6	41,2 ± 4,1	37,8 ± 3,3	42,9 ± 3,3	60,1 ± 6,6
AST	59,1 ± 3,3	69,1 ± 9,9	54,3 ± 4,0	43,6 ± 3,7	64,9 ± 5,5	129,7 ± 37,6
ALB	3,4 ± 0,04	3,2 ± 0,04	3,5 ± 0,06	3,3 ± 0,05	3,3 ± 0,05	2,95 ± 0,05
GGT	128,7 ± 14,4	127,8 ± 13,9	106,4 ± 14,4	107,1 ± 17,8	155,6 ± 26,3	152,8 ± 21,8
GLUK	178,5 ± 9,3	166,8 ± 7,1	167,1 ± 13,2	141,5 ± 6,7	192,2 ± 12,8	197,3 ± 12,3
FERRIT	1459,9 ± 219,2	1662,8 ± 442,6	959,2 ± 89,9	666,5 ± 57,4	2064,3 ± 461,3	2865,3 ± 955,1
LDH	539,0 ± 20,7	615,8 ± 57,2	472,7 ± 24,6	374,9 ± 23,1	619,0 ± 32,0	906,6 ± 112,1
D DIMER	3718,0 ± 503,4	3968,0 ± 592,7	3301,5 ± 656,3	2004,2 ± 258,8	4220,8 ± 780,1	6338,1 ± 1203,9
INR	1,21 ± 0,02	1,14 ± 0,05	1,19 ± 0,03	1,29 ± 0,03	1,23 ± 0,03	1,64 ± 0,1
PT	14,3 ± 0,8	15,8 ± 0,7	15,0 ± 1,5	14,6 ± 0,3	13,5 ± 0,05	17,4 ± 1,4
SPO2	82,2 ± 1,1	89,1 ± 1,6	82,8 ± 1,3	88,2 ± 1,3	81,4 ± 1,9	88,6 ± 1,6
TEMP	36,8 ± 0,06		36,8 ± 0,07		36,9 ± 0,1	
NLR	9,8 ± 0,8	12,8 ± 1,3	9,1 ± 0,7	6,1 ± 0,9	10,8 ± 1,4	20,8 ± 2,2

The most common conditions in COVID-19 patients are leukopenia, lymphopenia, and thrombocytopenia. It was 248.7±11.4 in the inpatient group and 242.1±8.4 in the resuscitation group. Another important biomarker, NLR, known as an indicator of inflammation and infection, is used for early disease prediction in COVID-19 patients.

As a novel inflammatory marker, NLR changes may not only reflect the role of neutrophils in infection but may also reflect changes in lymphocytes in vivo. It has been reported that NLR with influenza virus and other inflammation in the diagnosis and severity of the disease in patients with associated diseases has predictive value. Our results showed that NLR in the severe group was not significantly higher than in the heavy group. According to the research, it is observed that PCT and NLR levels of patients in severe critical groups are higher compared to the average group and CRP level is highest in the critically severe group. Studies have shown that PCT and CRP levels are associated with the severity of Covid-19 and the risk of complications from bacterial infections [17]. Therefore, the detection of NLR levels in COVID-19 patients was of great importance in assessing the severity of their condition.

The next most important biomarker is CRP, the investigation of which, together with NLR, may be necessary for early recognition of complications in Covid-19. CRP is a useful inflammatory marker and indicator that plays an important role in host resistance to pathogens and inflammation. CRP was highly correlated with acute lung injury in infected patients. Our study showed that CRP in the severe group was significantly

higher than in the non-severe group, and CRP was an independent risk factor for severe COVID-19.

Discussion

The main objective of this study was to investigate biomarkers that can accurately predict the severity of the coronavirus disease. Our analysis showed that CRP was significantly elevated in severe cases of COVID-19 compared to mild cases and was a significant predictor of disease severity. This result is consistent with a review article that concluded that CRP was present in 60.7% of patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 and was an important marker for predicting the prognosis of COVID-19 and disease severity in these patients [18]. The conclusion of Zheng et al. The identification of CRP as a significant marker for severe manifestation of COVID-19 is similar to ours; however, the ratio reported between severe and non-severe cases in their study is much higher than in our study.

Our study showed that LDH was significantly increased in patients with severe disease compared to patients with mild infections, thus demonstrating its role as the most potential biomarker in predicting the severity of COVID-19. Chen et al. also documented an association with elevated LDH levels in patients with severe disease [19]. The LDH levels of their study were two times lower than ours in both the severe and moderate patient groups, but their study as well as ours showed a significant relationship between LDH levels and disease severity.

The significance of ferritin as a biomarker for monitoring and predicting disease severity was lower in our study compared to CRP and LDH. This result differs from that reported by many other studies, most

of which identify serum ferritin as a significant marker for predicting disease severity [19,20]. A study in Wuhan, China, found a strong association of serum ferritin as a marker for severe disease [20]. Serum ferritin levels in our study were three times higher than those in the Wuhan study in both the mild-moderate and severe patient groups. The ferritin levels in that study were much lower than ours, but the association between ferritin levels and disease severity was statistically closer to our study, with our study reporting a p-value of 0.066 compared to theirs at admission. P-value 0.049 [19].

Our results also demonstrated the use of PCT as a significant disease biomarker, which is not similar to the results obtained by Gao et al., where the authors found no significant association between PCT and disease severity [6,20,21]. This association seen in our study between PCT and its predictability of disease severity may be due to higher rates of co-infection by bacteria.

Studies have shown the role of D-dimer as an effective predictor of COVID-19 mortality and, thus the severity of the disease. Most of the studies conducted to investigate the role of biomarkers in predicting the clinical features and severity of COVID-19 have shown that D-dimer is an effective predictor, and some have shown it to be an effective predictor of mortality and ARDS associated with the increase [19][20]. Our study concluded that D-dimer, along with PCT, was the second most effective biomarker after LDH in predicting disease severity, while CRP and ferritin were inferior to the aforementioned biomarkers in predicting critical status. The changes in coagulogram markers INR and PT were not effective in predicting the mildness and severity of the disease in our study.

We studied the impact of different biochemical markers in predicting COVID-19 and the order of effectiveness among the markers. Our results concluded that D-dimer, PCT, and LDH are superior to serum ferritin and CRP as effective biomarkers in predicting mortality of COVID-19. We also failed to establish significant associations of various other biomarkers in predicting the severity of coronavirus disease. Acute kidney injury and hypernatremia during the hospital course were also proven fatal events in our study. Such studies are critical and can be used as a guide when assessing the severity of the disease or when treating patients in this region.

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ВЕРТИКАЛЬНЫЕ ПОВРЕЖДЕНИЯ КОСТЕЙ ТАЗА. ЛЕЧЕНИЕ

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VERTICAL INJURIES OF THE PELVIC BONES. TREATMENT

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Аннотация

В работе представлен краткий обзор хирургических методов лечения повреждений тазового кольца. Описана оригинальная технология остеосинтеза при свежих смещенных полифокальных вертикальных переломах и повреждениях тазового кольца с использованием «Устройства для лечения смещенных переломов костей таза». Хирургическое вмешательство малотравматично. Представлена техника оперативного вмешательства, этапы остеосинтеза, особенности операции и инструмент для ее проведения. Определены принципы и этапы ведения больных.

Abstract

The paper presents a brief review of surgical methods for the treatment of pelvic ring injuries. The original technology of osteosynthesis for fresh displaced polyfocal vertical fractures and injuries of the pelvic ring using the "Device for the treatment of displaced pelvic fractures" is described. Surgical intervention is less traumatic. The technique of surgical intervention, the stages of osteosynthesis, the features of the operation and the tool for its implementation are presented. The principles and stages of patient management are determined.

Ключевые слова: повреждения тазового кольца, хирургическое лечение.

Keywords: pelvic ring injuries, surgical treatment.

Переломы костей таза встречаются в 5-10 % случаев закрытой травмы [2, с.6; 3, с.30], а в 15,0-36,8% из них - тяжелые переломы таза сочетаются с повреждениями органов брюшной полости и малого таза [1, с.215].

Переломы костей таза в основном являются следствием так называемой, «высокоэнергетической травмы», частота которой в последнее время неуклонно растет.

Переломы костей таза относятся к наиболее тяжелым повреждениям, сопровождающимся, как правило, явлениями шока и кровопотерей в остром